

THE ROLE OF CRITICAL THINKING IN THE RESEARCH WRITING PROCESS IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Annotation. In this thesis, it is given the importance of critical thinking in each stage of research writing assignments given to students in higher education.

Key words. interpret evidence, data, arguments, assignment question, information globalization, academic writing.

In contemporary society, the emphasis on higher education is increasing for various reasons. As one of the reasons, it is possible to cite the fact that in recent years, students are surrounded by a wide range of information in the era of globalization. As a result, in higher education, students need to have the ability to draw the most accurate conclusion by analyzing and synthesizing each received information while writing written assignments. In this situation, the role of critical thinking is very important. When critical thinking is applied to writing, the above abilities are expressed through the process of argumentation, producing an argument i.e. the essay, the dissertation. Argument can be defined as a connected series of related ideas “intended to establish a position and implying response to another (or more than one) position” (Andrews 1995). Argument is regarded as the primary expression of critical thinking in higher education (Andrews 1995, Scott 2000), and the defining feature of the essay (Elander et al. 2006). As Bonnett (2001) emphasizes: “Your essay is your argument, everything else makes sense because of it” [1]. Good writing is therefore a reflection of good critical thinking. The sources of ideas can be from across a variety of texts and those based on observation, experience and reflection (Vardi, 1999). Hence, critical thinking in academic writing is a manifestation of an author’s ability to understand and analyse the ideas, evaluate and synthesise the arguments in a variety of sources before making any conclusions, and then presenting them clearly to an audience [2].

Every research writing work consists of an introduction, several chapters, several body paragraphs and conclusion.

In the introduction, it is necessary to select a central problem or argument. Any information written in this section gives an idea of what the whole case is about. therefore, the idea to be written in this section should be chosen with the help of critical thinking in such a way that the reader fully understands what the text is about as soon as he reads the introduction. For this, it is necessary to have a good understanding of the content of the work to be written. Being able to

understand and create structured, reasoned arguments is central to critical thinking.

The process of writing the body paragraph, the critical thinking process consists several steps. They can include: reflection, analysis, gathering of information, creativity, structuring arguments, decision making, commitment and debate. In order to write a good writing work, the writer writes something understandable to the reader if he writes the body paragraph looking at these elements of critical thinking. Reflective thinking helps learners develop higher-order thinking skills by prompting learners to a) relate new knowledge to prior understanding, b) think in both abstract and conceptual terms, c) apply specific strategies in novel tasks, and d) understand their own thinking and learning strategies. Critical analysis allows you to have greater clarity on the issues and information you process. Academic disciplines are kept alive through constant reflection, debate and refinement of ideas. Critical analysis is thus crucial to the survival and renewal of all fields of enquiry. When information is gathered, researchers are able to get all of the information that they will need to think of a question. It helps them solve problems and make difficult decisions. Creativity benefits from our recognizing the role of critical thinking in ensuring the value of novel ideas. In turn, critical thinking comes into clearer focus when we recognize it +as a creative act that enriches understanding by giving rise to something that wasn't there before. The basic structure of every argument is essentially the same: two or more premises lead to a conclusion. The premises of an argument are its supporting structure. They're statements that provide evidence in support of the conclusion of the argument. Essentially, this is a process for thinking clearly through several options and arriving at the best choice. The ultimate goal of decision making is to arrive at actionable conclusions, and critical thinking is the process that proves whether the conclusion is sound.

In the conclusion part, authors should restate a thesis statement, summarize the main body points, and make a concluding remark. Finally, other essential features that learners should use in the main text are transitions to give a critical thinking paper a natural and logical flow of ideas and arguments [3].

In conclusion, the importance of critical thinking should not be forgotten in every academic writing work written in higher education. Critical thinking-based research work in higher education is easy to understand and every information to be given is based on facts. In turn, the writing of such scientific

works in the future can make a significant contribution to the development of science.

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